

Research Article

**The Effect of Consumer Load Balancing on the Maintenance of Power
Distribution Network**

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Abstract

The basis of an efficient functioning of a power grid is an accurate balancing of the electricity demand of all the consumers at any instant with supply. A balanced load in an electrical panel means the neutral current is zero. Load balancing results into significant energy saving opportunities as well as very significant electrical facility maintenance cost. The case study is the University of Jos 11KV dedicated feeder and its electrical distribution network. There has been an exponential increase in the maintenance cost of the network from the power transformer to the distribution board at the various electricity supply distribution points. Most of the high tension breaker, distribution transformers, feeder pillars and the distribution boards have been getting burnt. This led to monitoring of the phase load of each of the transformers on the dedicated feeder, and it was observed that most of the loads at the feeder pillars were unbalanced. Attempts towards balancing the load led to significant reduction in maintenance cost of the feeder to 40%. This shows that load balancing not only leads to energy saving, but also significant maintenance cost saving as well.

Key Words: Efficient Load Balancing, Dedicated Feeder, Maintenance.

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Introduction

The basis of an efficient functioning of a power grid is an accurate balancing of the electricity demand of all the consumers at any instant with supply. Load balancing, load matching, or daily peak demand reserve refers to the use of various techniques by electrical power stations to store excess electrical power during low demand periods for release as demand rises. The goal would be for the power supply system to see a load factor of 1 (Wikipedia, 2017). According to Zafar (2015) a quick-win power saving methodology of

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distribution system is balancing current along three-phase circuits. Feeder phase balancing also tends to balance voltage drop among phases giving three-phase customers less voltage unbalance. Current magnitude at the substation doesn't guarantee load is balanced throughout the feeder length. Feeder phase unbalance may vary during the day and with different seasons. Feeders are usually considered "balanced" when phase current magnitudes are within 10%. Similarly, balancing load among distribution feeders will also lower losses assuming similar conductor resistance. This may require installing additional switches between feeders to allow for appropriate load transfer. The phase voltage and current unbalances in the low voltage distribution network are major factors leading to extra losses, interference in communication, equipment overloading and malfunctioning of the protective relay. It consequently results in the reduction of service quality and operation efficiency. Phase unbalance is also manifested in increased complex power unbalance, increased power loss, enhanced voltage drop, and increased neutral current. When a single phase consumer is effected service connection it has to be ensured every time that low voltage network is balanced after effecting the service connection. For effective and efficient implementation existing network should be balanced by consumer (node) reconfiguration (Shodhganga, 2006). there are many benefits to balancing the loads of the two legs of power in your electrical panel and here's why. A balanced load in an electrical panel means that the current flowing through one leg is equal to the amount of current flowing through the other "hot" leg. The closer these numbers are, the more balanced the load. When the amperage is split up equally, the neutral current is canceled out. But when the current is placed all on one leg, the neutral must carry the entire load (Thiele, 2017). According to Fluke Corporation (2007), electrical unbalance can be caused by several different sources: a power delivery problem, low voltage on one leg, or an insulation resistance breakdown inside the motor windings. Even a small voltage unbalance can cause connections to deteriorate, reducing the amount of voltage supplied, while motors and other loads will draw excessive current, deliver lower torque (with associated mechanical stress), and fail sooner. A severe unbalance can blow a fuse, reducing operations down to a single phase. Meanwhile, the unbalanced current will return on the neutral, causing the utility to fine the facility for peak power usage. In practice, it is virtually impossible to perfectly balance the voltages across three phases. The National Electrical Manufacturers Association (NEMA) defines unbalance as a percentage: $\% \text{ unbalance} = \frac{[(100) (\text{maximum deviation from average voltage})]}{\div \text{average voltage}}$. To help equipment operators determine acceptable levels of unbalance, the NEMA has drafted specifications for multiple devices. These baselines are a useful point of comparison during maintenance and

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troubleshooting. Olufeagba and Alowolodu (2007), pointed out that power distribution in Nigeria is done predominantly at 415V phase-phase on 3-phase, 4-wire system. Usually, transformers rated between 50 and 500kVA are used at substations to supply groups of residential and commercial consumers in a radial manner. The high demand for electricity has resulted in overloading at most substations which leads to frequent outage and other anomalies. For the 3-phase system to function with minimum power loss, the loads on the phase must be balanced or as close to balanced as possible. This amongst other requires that the load be balanced. Load balancing is the process whereby loads/consumers are shared amongst the phases in such a manner that the total load at any time on each phase will be approximately equal.

Handhal and Rashid (2018), programmed heuristic algorithm using values which represented the three-phase currents of 20 houses. Each house assumed to have a smart energy meter connected with some contractors used for current balancing by phases swapping. Three cases were programmed using the heuristic algorithm to study the effect of used different numbers of contractors in each house. All the cases showed high performance in loads balancing and reduced the imbalance index.

Arias *et al.* (2019), used integer linear programming and Branch and Bound algorithm to balance the loads in the three phases of the distribution system, employing stored data of power demand. Results showed that the method helped to decrease the unbalance factor in more than 10%, by selecting the phase where a load should be connected. The solution may be used as a planning tool in distribution systems applied to installations with systems for measuring power consumption in different time intervals. Furthermore, in conjunction with communications and processing technologies, the solution could be useful to implement with a smart grid.

Materials and Methods

What is unbalance?

Any deviation in voltage and current waveform from perfect sinusoidal, in terms of magnitude or phase shift is termed as unbalance. In ideal conditions i.e. with only linear loads connected to the system, the phases of power supply are 120 degree apart in terms of phase angle and magnitude of their peaks should be same. On distribution level, the load imperfections cause current unbalance which travel to transformer and cause unbalance in the three phase voltage. Even minor unbalance in the voltage at transformer level

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disturbs the current waveform significantly on all the loads connected to it. Not only in the distribution side but through the transformer, voltage unbalances disturbs the high voltage power system as well.

Causes of unbalance

Practical imperfections which can result in unbalances are:-

1. A three phase equipment such as induction motor with unbalance in its windings. If the reactance of three phases is not same, it will result in varying current flowing in three phases and give out system unbalance.
 - With continuous operation, motor's physical environment cause degradation of rotor and stator windings. This degradation is usually different in different phases, affecting both, the magnitude and phase angel of current waveform.
 - A current leakage from any phase through bearings or motor body provides floating earth at times, causing fluctuating current.
2. Any large single phase load, or a number of small loads connected to only one phase cause more current to flow from that particular phase causing voltage drop on line.
3. Switching of three phase heavy loads results in current and voltage surges which cause unbalance in the system.
4. Unequal impedance in the power transmission or distribution system cause differentiating current in three phases.

How to calculate unbalance

Unbalance is calculated in terms of maximum deviation of current in a phase from the mean of three phases. To calculate the percentage deviation-

$$\frac{\text{Max}\{(I_m - I_r), (I_m - I_y), (I_m - I_b)\}}{I_m} * 100\%$$

Where I_m is mean of currents in three phases, {i.e. $I_m = \frac{(I_r + I_y + I_b)}{3}$ }
 I_r, I_y, I_b are phase currents.

Besides, an unbalance can also be quantified by comparing the intensity of negative sequence currents in comparison to the positive sequence currents. The permissible limit in terms of percentage of negative phase sequence current over positive sequence current is 1.3% ideally but acceptable up to 2%.

Effects of unbalance:

1. The unbalance decreases the motor efficiency by causing extra heating in the motor. Heat generated also effect the equipment life by increasing the operating temperature, which decompose the grease or oil in the bearing and de-rate the motor windings.

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2. In induction motors connected to unbalanced supply, the negative sequence currents flow along with positive sequence current resulting in decreased percentage of productive current and poor motor efficiency. Any unbalance above 3% hampers the motor efficiency.
3. Torque (and thus the speed) produced by the motor becomes fluctuating. These sudden changes in torque cause more vibration in the gear box or the equipment connected to it. The vibration and noise produced damages the equipment and also reduces the efficiency of equipment.
4. The variable frequency or speed drives connected to an unbalanced system can trip off. VFD treats high level unbalances as phase fault and can trip on earth fault or missing phase fault.
5. Unbalances cause de-rating of power cables and thus increase I²R losses in the cable. For distribution cables de-rating factor represents the part of total current giving fruitful outcomes.
6. UPS or inverter supplies also perform with poor efficiency and inject more harmonic currents in case of unbalances in the system.
7. Negative phase sequence current flowing due to unbalance can cause faults in the motor, resulting in, tripping or permanent damage of the electrical equipment. (Zenatix, 2015).

There various methods of load balancing among which are;

(i) Load estimation before connection

Estimates of the load are used as the basis for allocating the phase to which a consumer is connected in the first instance when being first energized.

(ii) Consumer Ad-hoc Approach

~~~~~This is response of helpless consumers to the extreme conditions which damage their equipment and curtail their access to quality electric power. In Nigeria this problem is further exacerbated by the frequent occurrence of single and two phase faults where consumers observe their neighbours having power whilst they languish in darkness.

**(iii) Automatic Change Over**

~~~~~It is easy to imagine an automated system which depends on imprecisely stated guidelines to select the phase with the best voltage each time and in addition includes other criteria that will prevent systemic oscillations. The third method is a theoretical one whereby an automaton which may use a microcontroller is installed at each loading point and can be directed by some central authority through the agency of another automaton to periodically adjust the phase of each consumer. Naturally, this method has many advantages which however introduce additional but complex equipment at each installation (Olufeagba and Alowolodu, 2007).

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Control Measures for Unbalanced Loads

1. All the single phase loads should be distributed on the three phase system such that they put equal load on three phases.
2. Replacing the disturbing equipment i.e. with unbalanced three phase reactance.
3. Reducing the harmonics also reduces the unbalance, which can be done by installing reactive or active filters. These filters reduce the negative phase sequence currents by injecting a compensating current wave.
4. In case the disturbing loads cannot be replaced or repaired, connect them with high voltage side this reduces the effects in terms of percentage and even controlled disturbance in low voltage side.
5. Motors with unbalanced phase reactance should be replaced and re-winded.

University of Jos 11kv Dedicated Feeder.

This paper is not adopting any of the methods above this is because the work is being carried out on an existing 11kv dedicated feeder network as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The University of Jos 11KV dedicated feeder, Jos Business Unit

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The University of Jos 11KV dedicated feeder is made up of 16 transformers and about 8.7Km of distribution line. The main Power transformer is 7.5MVA as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. List of Transformers and Locations

| S/N | Location | Capacity Rating (KVA) |
|-----|--|-----------------------|
| 1 | Central Library | 500 |
| 2 | Geology Department | 300 |
| 3 | Lecture Theatre (Sky Bank) | 500 |
| 4 | Naraguta Staff Qtrs/Works | 500 |
| 5 | Education Sub-station (1) | 500 |
| 6 | Education Sub-station (2) | 500 |
| 7 | Naraguta Female Hostel (ZION) | 500 |
| 8 | Naraguta Male Hostel | 750 |
| 9 | Abuja Female Hostel | 500 |
| 10 | Abuja Male Hostel | 1000 |
| 11 | Medical Sciences | 500 |
| 12 | Natural Sciences | 500 |
| 13 | Students Village Hostel | 500 |
| 14 | Bauchi Road Senior Staff Quarters, Transformer #1. | 300 |
| 15 | Bauchi road Senior Staff Quarters, Transformer #2 | 300 |
| | Total Distribution Transformer | 7,650 |
| 16 | Main Injection Substation Power Transformer (Naraguta Main Campus Entrance Gate) | 7500 |

The phase load of each of the transformer was recorded for a period of six months in order to put right those transformers that have unbalanced phase load above the acceptable limit of 10% as recommended by ANSI.

The percentage Unbalanced load can be calculated using the formula below;
 $\% \text{ Unbalanced Load} = \frac{[(\text{Maximum deviation from average}) / \text{Average}] \times 100\%}{100\%}$.

An example can be made with the Central library load in Table 2.
 $\% \text{ Unbalanced Load} = (28.46 + 27.58 + 31.21) / 3 = 87.25 / 3 = 29.08\%$

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Maximum deviation from the average = $31.21 - 29.08 = 2.12A$

% Unbalanced = $(2.12A/29.08A)*100\% = 7.29\%$

The figure is below the maximum unbalanced load of 10%.

The remaining load values for the other transformers are as tabulated in Table 2.

Table 2. Transformer Average Phase Load

| S/N | Transformer | Red Phase(A) | Yellow Phase(A) | Blue Phase(A) | Max.Unbalanced Load (A) | % Unbalance |
|-----|--|--------------|-----------------|---------------|-------------------------|-------------|
| 1 | Central Library | 28.46 | 27.58 | 31.21 | 2.12 | 7.29 |
| 2 | Geology Department | 11.19 | 13.47 | 10.78 | 1.42 | 11.78 |
| 3 | Lecture Theatre(Skye Bank) | 16.37 | 17.16 | 19.13 | 1.57 | 8.98 |
| 4 | Naraguta Staff Qtrs/Works | 35.81 | 37.27 | 40.13 | 2.39 | 6.34 |
| 5 | Education Sub-station (1) | 13.46 | 15.07 | 12.78 | 1.3 | 9.44 |
| 6 | Education Sub-station (2) | 11.17 | 12.69 | 16.13 | 2.8 | 12.01 |
| 7 | Naraguta Female Hostel | 27.31 | 33.45 | 35.67 | 3.53 | 10.97 |
| 8 | Naraguta Male Hostel | 20.17 | 35.32 | 41.51 | 9.18 | 28.38 |
| 9 | Abuja Female Hostel | 31.26 | 29.45 | 33.21 | 1.9 | 6.07 |
| 10 | Abuja Male Hostel | 44.62 | 36.13 | 29.67 | 7.81 | 21.23 |
| 11 | Medical Sciences | 26.6 | 27.3 | 30.7 | 2.5 | 8.86 |
| 12 | Natural Sciences | 20.7 | 23.2 | 21.9 | 1.27 | 5.79 |
| 13 | Students Village Hostel | 23.6 | 31.3 | 18.5 | 7.03 | 28.73 |
| 14 | Bauchi Road Senior Staff Quarters, Transformer #1. | 17 | 36 | 28 | 9 | 33 |
| 15 | Bauchi Road Senior Staff Quarters, Transformer #2 | 27.4 | 29.2 | 32.5 | 2.8 | 9.43 |

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The cost of maintenance work carried out on the listed transformers above during a period of four years is tabulated as in Table 3.

Table 3. Cost of Maintenance on Transformers

| S/
N | Transformer | Transformer
Maintenance
(₦) | Skipper
panel/Up riser &
XLPE Cables
(₦) | Feeder
Pillar
(₦) |
|---------|--|-----------------------------------|---|-------------------------|
| 1 | Central Library | Routine | Nil | Nil |
| 2 | Geology
Department | 550,000.00 | Nil | Nil |
| 3 | Lecture
Theatre(Skye Bank) | Routine | Nil | Nil |
| 4 | Naraguta Staff
Qtrs/Works | Routine | Nil | Nil |
| 5 | Education
Sub-station (1) | Routine | Nil | Nil |
| 6 | Education
Sub-station (2) | 250,000.00 | Nil | Nil |
| 7 | Naraguta Female
Hostel | Routine | 365,000.00 | 259,000.00 |
| 8 | Naraguta Male
Hostel | Routine | 478,653.50 | 125,670.00 |
| 9 | Abuja Female
Hostel | Routine | Nil | Nil |
| 10 | Abuja Male
Hostel | 124,320.00 | Nil | 463,765.00 |
| 11 | Medical Sciences | Routine | Nil | 450,000.00 |
| 12 | Natural Sciences | Routine | Nil | Nil |
| 13 | Students Village
Hostel | Routine | 478,654.00 | 597,345.00 |
| 14 | Bauchi Road Senior
Staff Quarters,
Transformer #1. | Routine | 1,156,842.60 | 896,574.65 |
| 15 | Bauchi road Senior
Staff Quarters,
Transformer #2 | Routine | Nil | Nil |

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Results/Analysis

Table 4. Balanced Transformer Average Phase Load

| S/
N | Transformer | Red
Phase(A) | Yellow
Phase
(A) | Blue
Phase
(A) | Max.Unbalanc
ed Load (A) | %
Unbalance |
|---------|---|-----------------|------------------------|----------------------|-----------------------------|----------------|
| 1 | Central Library | 28.46 | 27.58 | 31.21 | 2.12 | 7.29 |
| 2 | Geology
Department | 12.02 | 11.98 | 11.44 | 0.21 | 1.78 |
| 3 | Lecture Theatre
(Skye Bank) | 16.37 | 17.16 | 19.13 | 1.57 | 8.98 |
| 4 | Naraguta Staff
Qtrs/Works | 35.81 | 37.27 | 40.13 | 2.39 | 6.34 |
| 5 | Education
Sub-station (1) | 13.46 | 15.07 | 12.78 | 1.3 | 9.44 |
| 6 | Education
Sub-station (2) | 13.26 | 12.72 | 14.01 | 0.68 | 5.1 |
| 7 | Naraguta Female
Hostel | 30.24 | 31.56 | 32.79 | 1.26 | 4.0 |
| 8 | Naraguta Male
Hostel | 30.75 | 33.48 | 32.55 | 1.22 | 3.78 |
| 9 | Abuja Female
Hostel | 31.26 | 29.45 | 33.21 | 1.9 | 6.07 |
| 10 | Abuja Male
Hostel | 36.73 | 36.65 | 37.81 | 0.98 | 2.65 |
| 11 | Medical Sciences | 26.6 | 27.3 | 30.7 | 2.5 | 8.86 |
| 12 | Natural Sciences | 20.7 | 23.2 | 21.9 | 1.27 | 5.79 |
| 13 | Students Village
Hostel | 25.41 | 24.67 | 23.98 | 0.72 | 2.92 |
| 14 | Bauchi Road
Senior Staff
Quarters,
Transformer #1. | 26.34 | 27.63 | 28.12 | 0.76 | 2.78 |
| 15 | Bauchi Road
Senior Staff
Quarters,
Transformer #2 | 27.4 | 29.2 | 32.5 | 2.8 | 9.43 |

From Table 3 it can be seen that transformers 2, 6, 7, 8, 10, 13, and 14 all have percentage unbalanced above 10% limit. They have maintenance costs of ₦6,195,824.75 inclusive transformers 11 which has an unbalanced percentage of 8.86% and yet it had its feeder unit replaced with a new one. The other

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transformers had routine maintenance cost carried out which was an estimated average of N10, 000.00 per transformer.

The transformer loads have been checked and balanced as shown in Table 4.

After the load balancing there has been no major maintenance breakdown from the transformers which were unbalanced, which are transformers; 2, 6, 7, 8, 10, 13, and 14. However the routine hourly, daily, monthly and annual preventive maintenance was ongoing which included but not limited to checking of ambient temperature, winding temperature, oil temperature, load, voltage, oil level in transformer, oil level in bushing, cooler fan, bushing, gasket joints, cable boxes, relay alarm and other circuits, earth resistance, arcing contact, and feeder pillar fuse holders, among others.

Conclusion

Load balancing has a significant effect on power supply quality and savings in maintenance cost. Whenever an unbalance of current occurs in the system there exists a neutral current which causes energy loss. Ideally any distribution transformer gives best performance at 50% loading and every electrical distribution system is designed for it but in case of unbalance the loading goes over 50% as the equipment draw more current (Zenatix, 2015). Further reduction of power losses caused by unbalanced state can be achieved through the implementation of measures to balance the load, starting with substations identified with highly unbalanced degree. There is the need to ensure that load balancing is carried out at the early stage of every electrical installation and periodically thereafter as this will go a long way into ensuring good power quality and savings in billings and maintenance cost. It will also reduce the incidence of fire outbreak. In this work attempt towards balancing the load led to significant reduction in maintenance cost of the feeder by 40%. This shows that load balancing not only leads to energy saving, but also significant maintenance cost saving as well.

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